

Physico-chemical Studies of Some Transition Metal Complexes of Vanillin-Hydrazone

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Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Mn(II) and Fe(III) complexes of a Schiff base derived from vanillin and hydrazine (Van-Hy) have been prepared and characterised on the basis of element analyses, infrared and electronic spectra and magnetic susceptibility measurements. The magnetic and spectral data indicate them to be low spin octahedral complexes. Van-Hy acts as the bidentate O-O donor.

HYDRAZIDES and their derivatives are considered to function as antitubercular compounds because of their ability to form more or less stable metal chelates¹⁻³. In recent years there has been considerable interest^{4,5} in the synthesis and physico-chemical properties of these metal chelates as they are shown to possess unusual magnetic and structural properties. In continuation of our studies on transition metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from vanillin⁶, we report here the results of our studies on the synthesis and characterisation of Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Mn(II) and Fe(III) complexes of vanillin-hydrazone (Van-Hy).

Experimental

All chemicals used were A.R. or S.M. grade.

Preparation of Van-Hy: The Schiff base was prepared by refluxing aqueous solutions of hydrazine sulphate and vanillin in equimolar ratio. The orange-yellow Schiff base was filtered, washed and dried with ether, m.p. 214°, soluble in alcohol, dioxane and alkali and sparingly soluble in acetone. The m.p. and molecular weight (ebullioscopy; ethanol as solvent) confirmed formation of 1:1 Schiff base, $C_8H_8(OH)(OCH_3)(CH)=NNH_2$ ⁷.

Preparation of the metal complexes: Metal complexes of the Schiff base were prepared by refluxing aqueous solutions of $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$, $MnSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$, $NiSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, $Fe(NH_4)_2(SO_4)_2 \cdot 6H_2O$, $CoSO_4 \cdot 7H_2O$, $Fe(NO_3)_3 \cdot 9H_2O$ and sodium salt of the Schiff base (prepared by dissolving the Schiff base in the just required quantity of a dil. solution of NaOH) in 1:2 molar ratio for 2 to 3 hr. The insoluble complexes separated out on cooling, were filtered, washed and dried in vacuum. They were analysed for metal, C, H and N microanalytically.

The magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out using the Gouy method at the room temperature (24°). Diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants. Infrared spectra

were recorded in KBr on a Perkin Elmer model 337 IR spectrophotometer and the electronic spectra were obtained on Beckmann spectrophotometer model 26. The results are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) indicate 1:2 (metal:ligand) stoichiometry for all the complexes with the molecular formula $ML_2 \cdot 2H_2O$. None of the complexes was found to melt below 300°. The complexes are insoluble in common organic solvents and water.

Magnetic susceptibility: The magnetic moments of the complexes (Table 1) indicate all of them to be spin-paired octahedral complexes. The subnormal values of μ_{eff} in some cases [Fe(III) and Cu(II) complexes] indicate dimeric structure in the solid state. The μ_{eff} value (2.8 B.M.) for Ni(II)-Van-Hy is typical of paramagnetic octahedral complex⁸, while those for Co(II)-Van-Hy (2.08 B.M.) and Mn(II)-Van-Hy (2.2 B.M.) are well within the range of the spin-paired octahedral stereochemistry. However, the value of 2.2 B.M. in the case of Mn(II) complex indicates large orbital contribution. The subnormal value for Cu(II)-Van-Hy (1.3 B.M.) indicates the presence of spin-only coupling by super exchange through the binding atoms. Thus, in the light of the previous observations⁹⁻¹² the low value may be assigned to a dimeric structure (III).

The magnetic moment value for Fe(II)-Van-Hy is quite abnormal (1.9 B.M.). The value is higher than the spin-only value for single electron, but very much lower than the value for high-spin octahedral or tetrahedral stereochemistry (4.9-5.7 B.M.). The spin-paired octahedral complexes of Fe(II) are diamagnetic, while low spin complexes of Fe(II) in tetrahedral geometry are rare and have two unpaired electrons (2.9-3.3 B.M.). The abnormal value of μ_{eff} for Fe(II)-Van-Hy obtained in this study indicates that Fe(II) is oxidised to Fe(III) by transfer of electron to the ligand and thus accounting for the

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC MOMENT DATA OF VAN-HY COMPLEXES

Complex	Colour	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} at 24° (B.M.)
		Metal	O	H	N	
Fe(Van-Hy) ₂ (OH).H ₂ O	Greenish brown	13.34 (18.24)	45.30 (45.51)	5.25 (5.21)	13.30 (13.27)	1.53
Mn(Van-Hy) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Yellow	13.10 (13.05)	45.34 (45.61)	5.26 (5.22)	13.27 (13.30)	2.18
Co(Van-Hy) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Brown yellow	13.91 (13.87)	45.33 (45.18)	5.22 (5.17)	13.15 (13.18)	2.08
Ni(Van-Hy) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Yellow green	13.85 (13.82)	45.42 (45.20)	5.12 (5.18)	13.06 (13.04)	2.78
Cu(Van-Hy) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Chocolate brown	14.81 (14.79)	44.53 (44.70)	5.15 (5.12)	13.10 (13.18)	1.30

 TABLE 2—BANDS IN IR SPECTRA (cm⁻¹) OF VAN-HY AND ITS COMPLEXES

Van-Hy	Iron		Co(II)	Ni(II)	Cu(II)	Mn(II)	Assignments
	1*	2**					
3500 s	3480 s	3480 s	3660-	3640-	3640-	3640-	$\nu(\text{OH})$
3300-2500 bs	3380-3020	3380-3020	3000	3000	3300	3300	Coord. H ₂ O H-bonded OH
1360 m	1380 w	1380 w	1365 w	1385 w	1385 w	1380 w	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$
1300	1315 vs	1315 vs	1325 vs	1310 vs	1320 vs	1320 vs	Phenolic
1265 vs	1285 vs	1285 vs	1270 vs	1280 vs	1290 vs	1275 vs	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$
1080	1035 vs	1030 s	1030 s	1080 s	1025 s	1020 s	Methoxy
1630 vs	1625 vs	1625 vs	1630 vs	1630 vs	1625 s	1625 s	$\nu(\text{OH}=\text{N})$
	815 m	815 s	890 m	895 s	825 n	825 m	Coord. H ₂ O
	480 m	425 m	435 m	435 m	430 w	435 m	(M-O)
	1540 s	1540 s	1540 s	1540 s	1550 s	1550 s	Polydentate oxygen

* (1) The complex isolated with the Fe(II) salt.

** (2) The complex isolated with the Fe(III) salt.

presence of single electron in octahedral stereochemistry. This conclusion finds support in the spectral study (discussed below) of the complex which indicates that the spectra obtained for the isolated Fe(II)-Van-Hy complex is characteristic of a Fe(III)-complex, rather than of a Fe(II)-complex.

The μ_{eff} value obtained for Fe(III)-Van-Hy (1.5 B.M.) is much less than the expected value for a spin-paired octahedral complex and again indicates its dimeric structure (III) in solid state.

Electronic spectra: Van-Hy did not show any band in the visible but showed three bands at 270, 320 and 350 nm in ultraviolet region. The first band corresponds to $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the perturbed benzene ring of the Schiff base fragment. The second band may be assigned to the whole aromatic molecule, oriented *trans* with respect to the double bond^{13,14}, while the third band corresponds to a $n-\pi^*$ transition due to charge transfer.

These bands in uv region are retained in the spectra of the metal complexes but showing a shift towards lower wavelengths as compared to the free ligand. However, it is roughly true that within the series of the metals these bands move to comparatively longer wavelengths as the oxidising power of the metal ion increases.

The ligand field spectra of Mn(II)-Van-Hy exhibit two bands at 18.2 and 29.4 kK due to

${}^2T_{2g}(I) \rightarrow {}^6A_{1g}(I)$ and ${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2T_{1g}(G)$ transitions, respectively showing octahedral stereochemistry¹⁵. In the case of Co(II)-Van-Hy, only one band is observed at 17.86 kK which may be assigned to ${}^2E_g(G) \rightarrow {}^2T_{1g}(G)$ transition in octahedral field¹⁶. Two bands have been observed in the electronic spectra of the Ni(II) complex due to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (15.5 kK) and ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (28.5 kK) transitions indicating octahedral geometry of the complex. The spectra of Fe(II) complex show three bands at 14.0, 17.0 and 19.7 kK, which are analogous to the bands obtained in the case of Fe(III) complexes in octahedral geometry¹⁷. Fe(II) complexes in octahedral environment give bands in the region 10.5 and 8.0 kK¹⁸. The spectra of the complex isolated in this study did not show absorptions in these regions. Thus, the occurrence of the bands at 14.0, 17.0 and 19.7 kK, characteristic of Fe(III) complexes¹⁷ in octahedral geometry confirms the oxidation of Fe(II) into Fe(III) during isolation, is in agreement with the magnetic study discussed earlier and can be assigned to ${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^6A_{1g}$ transition. Comparable bands have been obtained for the Fe(III)-Van-Hy complex isolated in this study at 16.4, 17.0 and 17.8 kK with the assignment ${}^2T_{2g} \rightarrow {}^6A_{1g}$. The well marked splitting of the band in the region of ~17.0 kK, in sharp contrast to the single band in Fe(III)-Van-Sul (vanillin-sulphanilate)¹⁹, indicates clearly the polymeric nature²⁰ of Fe(III)-Van-Hy in confirmation of the conclusion drawn

on the basis of magnetic study. Cu(II)-Van-Hy did not show any band in the visible region as d-d transitions are obscured by the intense CT band.

IR spectra : Characteristic ir frequencies of the Schiff base and their complexes along with their assignments are recorded in Table 2, which clearly indicate that Van-Hy molecules are attached with the metal ion through the phenolic -OH group (with deprotonation) and the methoxy oxygen of the vanillin residue. Presence of coordinated water molecules is also indicated in all the complexes.

IR spectra of the metal complexes do not show change in stretching frequency of the free -NH₂ group, which appears at ~3500 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of Van-Hy. This shows that the -NH₂ group of hydrazine residue is not involved in the coordination with the metal ion. However, disappearance of the band at ~2800 cm⁻¹ (due to hydrogen bonded -OH group of the ligand) in the metal complexes indicates deprotonation and complexation resulting in the σ-M bond formation²¹. The ν(C-O) appearing at ~1360 cm⁻¹ in free Van-Hy shifts to higher frequency by 20 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes along with the appearance of a band near 1540 cm⁻¹ (indicating the presence of a polydentate oxygen)²². These observations show that chelation of Van-Hy molecules with the metal ion has taken place through the phenolic and the methoxy oxygens forming a five membered ring.

A broad band near 3500-3000 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes indicates the presence of coordinated water molecules along with the free -NH₂ group²³. Presence of coordinated water finds further confirmation in the band at ~800 cm⁻¹^{24,25}.

In Cu(II)-Van-Hy and Fe(III)-Van-Hy which have been shown to have dimeric structures (as discussed above), there appears an additional band near 1120 cm⁻¹, which may be assigned to ν(O-O)²⁶ showing an O-O link in the dimer (structure III).

Further, appearance of a medium band at ~435 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes may be taken as an indication of the M-O bond in agreement with Singh *et al*²⁷.

In the light of the above discussion, the following general structures for the monomeric (II) and dimeric/polymeric molecules (III) of the complexes may be proposed.

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